

The Effective of Classroom Management on Nurturing

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Abstract—The primary purpose of this paper is to explain the impact of successful classroom management on the academic achievements of students, the importance of positive relationship between teacher and students, among students, between teacher and parents. Effective communication plays an important role to encourage students study hard and learn materials which are covered by the teacher in the class. Friendly relationships among students other than their preferred friends help them to have team working and be socialized. In addition, a well-organized classroom arrangement enhances students learning. As the consequence of successful classroom management students should feel responsibility and need to feel it. The one who is responsible to provide a comfortable environment and help students learn is the manager of the classroom who is named Teacher.

Keywords—Classroom management, positive relationship, effective communication, teacher, student.

I. INTRODUCTION

SCHOLARS in the field of education agree that each learning institution, primary or secondary, has its own culture. This culture can be different from one learning institution to another. Each institution has some general and specific written rules which regulate the system of working and oblige the staff to work according to what is written. There are also a set of unwritten rules which are needed to be followed by the same staff of the organization, this rules can be codes of behavior: how staff should dress, how they call each other, how teachers and students need to work together and how their problems can be solved. Even if you do not agree with them all, you must respect the institution which has employed you. Avoid taking matters into your own hands and rely on the advice of colleagues if problems arise. If you behave very differently from the rest of the staff then the students will not know where to place you and will not necessarily respect you as a staff member or a teacher.

According to a researcher like Lemov, effective teaching is an art. 'Great art relies on the mastery and application of foundational skills learned individually through diligent study' [6]

Therefore, principals and other administrators play an important role in establishing effective discipline throughout the school. Principals and other administrators lead in creating a vision for the organization, develop a philosophy of positive discipline, and establish an orderly environment through reasoned rules and policies. It's up to the leaders of the school to support teachers and model respectful human interaction. Positive reinforcement, as well as punishment, and corrective manner when needed should be provided by them.

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Good teachers make positive discipline happen in the classroom, on the playground, and in every other corner of the school every day of the year. A principal does not have to be the best disciplinarian in the school, but to know what good discipline looks like and what it takes to achieve it. The most powerful thing you can do to foster positive discipline in your school is to coach teachers in effective classroom management.

Where teachers are strong, effective principals support them and help them get even better. Where teachers are weak, principals have to teach them the secrets of successful classroom management and overall discipline. It begins by helping all teachers, beginners to understand the real-world dynamics of today's classroom. Controlling classroom behavior is not the same as it was a few years ago. Now the question is what does a teacher have to do to get students to apply themselves to their work and stop fooling around and being disruptive?

To achieve answer to the above question effective teachers have to master the art of managing their classroom, and in order for teachers to successfully teach and students to academically succeed; an orderly classroom environment with minimum disruption to bring behavior under control is needed. There should be a carefully planned technique system of procedures and rules that creates an atmosphere to learn.

This paper will examine the progressive ideology that teachers should be able to help students govern themselves and the conservative ideology of a structured classroom environment and their effects on students' academic achievement.

II. THE IMPORTANCE OF CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Classroom management is important to everyone connected with education. As Larrivee points in the past, classroom management has often been seen as an issue of dealing with individual behavior. According to many theorists on the subject of classroom management who agree that the best way to achieve a well-managed classroom proceeding is through advance planning which aims at preventing delays, distractions and disruptions. They maintain that classroom management does not discount possibility of learner disruptions that may demand action from the teacher to maintain discipline in the classroom. [5]

During the 1970's and 1980's Classroom management first became a popular topic in education. Behavior management was the primarily focus of this period and it is used to control and shape students' behavior to conform to school rules. The classroom teacher uses consequences, rewards and punishment to guide students to conform to the rules. To repress disorderly behavior an authoritarian or punitive approach were used in

classroom management, but it did not enhance student's critical thinking and reflection.

Nowadays few aspects of education have generated as much concern as classroom management and organization. These aspects are among the most frequently addressed topics for teachers in service; they head the list of concerns of school administrators and have recently attracted more attention from teacher educators and researchers because a teacher's ability to effectively manage the classroom and to organize instruction is basic components of teaching. Moreover as classroom management strategies have a strong potential to positively influence students' achievement and learning, they are important concern for many teachers, especially novices and teachers who are contemplating new instructional approaches for the first time.

Many studies have proven that classroom management is one of the crucial factors that influence learning. It is identified the classroom management as being the first in a list of important factors that influence school learning. Another researcher like Marzano identified classroom management as the most important factor influencing school learning. [8]

Throughout the history the term classroom management has been defined differently by various educators. In most general terms, classroom management refers to the actions and strategies that teachers use to maintain order [3].

For many years, traditional approaches were dominant in teaching and learning practices in Kurdish schools. They were mostly based on the behavioral principles and laws of learning. The child was often viewed as the recipient of knowledge and teacher had the control over the students and subject matter. As a result, teachers preferred behavioral classroom management techniques that are consistent with their way of instruction. The behavioral model needs strong intrusion and management techniques on the part of the teacher. The teacher is the leading person who has the responsibility of all ongoing issues in the classroom, from students' encouragement to misbehaviors.

Over the past years, cognitive theories reflections have been observed on education. The curriculum and instruction have been affected by the principles of constructivist approach all over the world [4]. With the advent of constructivism, the educational settings have been enriched by the concept of 'student-centered learning environment'. The new concept is used to describe curriculum and instructional settings in which students' learning activities take place. The student-centered orientation emphasizes the individual value of the student and attempts to help him develop more positive social- emotional aspects of his behavior.

A good classroom organization integrates students' needs, interests, experiences, and personalization into learning activities. Classroom activities should be designed to facilitate self-expression, to encourage consideration of the viewpoint of another, to increase creative acts, to develop purposeful listening and to encourage critical thinking.

In most so-called student-centered learning environments learners are presented with an authentic task in order to induce relevant learning experiences. For instance, rather than

presenting information on global warming to students in a lecture, students are asked to make a report on the changing weather conditions in their own region.

As a result of this change in the curriculum and instructional approaches, teachers should adapt their approaches to classroom management. Such a shift requires teachers to adopt a student-centered rather than teacher-centered orientation toward classroom management, which features shared relationship and community building. In the student-centered system the role of teacher changes from a control agent, who is dominant in the classroom, makes all the decisions and demands respect from the students, into a guide who facilitates students' learning, encourages students' efforts and is open to discussions. According to the categorization of Martin and Baldwin, the teachers implementing behavioral techniques are more controlling and interventionist while the teachers implementing constructivist techniques should be inter-actionist and non-interventionist. Such a transition, however, will only be successful when the main actors, i.e. teachers and students, understand and agree with the keystones of so-called student-centered learning environments. The transition period of curriculum surely necessitates adaptations of learners' and teachers' roles in the learning environment as well as in the actual interactions. In order for the achievement of the objectives of student-centered classrooms to enhance the students' sense of responsibility and empower them, it is essential that teacher's role changes from an authoritarian figure to a guide. [7]

In accordance with the current trends in education throughout the world, the Elementary School Curriculum was revised in Iraqi Kurdistan and designed according to the main principles of constructivist learning theory. This large-scale curriculum reform has been implemented since the beginning of 21st century in primary and secondary schools in country level. This reform aimed at major changes in the school programs in all subjects and has been described as constructivist education reform. In accordance with the changes in the curriculum, teachers have needed to adapt their classroom management techniques strategies into the learning environment while trying to achieve the constructivist curriculum objectives; however, there have been such a number of studies conducted to explore the effectiveness of constructivist curriculum since the process of the reform.

III. THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The determination of the Art of Classroom Management in the basic schools in Iraqi Kurdistan/Sulaimani Governorate has been aimed in this study. Under the scope of the study a questionnaire which is includes 19 questions has been constructed.

IV. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This descriptive study was employed to assert the existing circumstances of the Art of Classroom Management which is preferred by the teachers of basic schools of Iraqi Kurdistan/Sulaimani Governorate.

V. SAMPLING

The sample of this study consists of 100 teachers teaching in the 6th, 7th, 8th and 9th grades. The survey was conducted in the fall of the 2012-2013 academic year in the governorate of Sulaimani. In the sample selection, the convenience sampling method was used. The data were collected from 25 schools from 10 different districts of the city. The questionnaire was answered by those teachers who were ready to provide contribution in line with the purpose of the study.

As it is shown in the Table I, a total of 100 teachers have participated in the study consisting of 25 for each of the 6th, 7th, 8th, and 9th grades.

TABLE I
 THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE PARTICIPANTS OF THE STUDY ACCORDING TO THEIR GRADES

Grade	Frequency	%
6th	25	25
7th	25	25
8th	25	25
9th	25	25
Total	100	100

TABLE II
 DISTRIBUTION OF TEACHERS ACCORDING TO THEIR GENDERS

Gender	Frequency	%
Male	43	43
Female	57	57
Total	100	100

As it is shown in the Table II, the number of female teachers are more than their opposite gender partners.

VI. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The questionnaire constructed by experts, the data collected from 6th, 7th, 8th, and 9th grade basic school teachers. The result of the study is shown in tables with their frequencies and percentages.

VII. CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

No matter you have just started teaching or experiencing several years of teaching career, your classroom management skills will have an important impact on how much your students learn and how satisfied you are with your role as a teacher. Research indicates that teachers' skills in creating safe, supportive classrooms are a key factor influencing student's motivation, achievement, and behavior.

As it is clear today, most of the classrooms are being occupied by those young students who are endowed with their own abilities, needs, interests, age, sex, behavior, social background etc. In order to secure effective and consistent classroom instruction, without creating a wider gap in a single four walled room, special management strategies are necessary.

Read the statements about classroom Management Strategies and then put a tick in the box according to the rating scales below:

Strong agree = 5; Agree = 4; Uncertain = 3; Disagree = 2; Strong disagree = 1

According to the data of our study, Positive Relationship is an important aspect of effective classroom management. One might make the case that teacher-student relationships are the keystone for the other factors. When the teacher has a good relationship with students, then they more readily accept the rules and procedures that follow their violations. If a good relationship between the teacher and students is not found then students commonly resist rules.

So when rethinking classroom management, the quality of the teacher-student relationship should be considered as a single most important factor. Positive relationships are the foundation of any classroom. These will be the key to a safe and caring classroom climate that invites and supports positive behavior and skilled problem solving. The type of relationships between students and teachers, among students, and between parents and teachers can be significant contributors to the classroom environment.

Data regarding Effective Teacher-student Relationships statement prove that the teachers' skill in managing their class depends on the quality of their relationship with the children. It is essential to start with a new class in the right way by building positive and respectful relationships from the outset. Therefore, teachers must build up trust and friendship with the students as an important approach to establish the basis for behavioral management and change.

It is generally agreed that the teacher-student relationship is badly important, but it is not easy and takes time and trust to be built. To achieve this, both sides must believe they are being treated with dignity and respect, and at the same time there must be a balance between the teacher's role as classroom leader and his or her expression of interest in each student.

Teachers need to establish obvious behavioral expectations and meaningful goals for learning and behavior, and they need to follow up them consistently. When Students know that their teacher cares about them and their individual needs then they trust and respect their teacher, and this can be achieved by having flexible learning goals which are enough to accommodate differences between and among students and at the same time the teacher can understand the individual needs, strengths, interests, learning preferences and personality of the students.

Effective teacher-student relationships have nothing to do with the teacher's personality or even with whether the students view the teacher as a friend. Rather, specific teacher behaviors can be the most effective teacher-student relationships.

Almost all the participant teachers in the survey agreed that the cornerstone of education is effective communication. If there is no effective communication thoughts, directions, and ideas are lost or misunderstood.

One of the important elements of the art of classroom management is an effective communication which may affect how students perceive and respond to a teacher's communication.

TABLE III
THE CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

Classroom Management Strategies	1		2		3		4		5	
	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
Positive Relationships	2	2	1	1	32	32	34	31	31	31
Effective Teacher-student Relationships	5	5	3	3	24	24	30	30	48	48
Effective Communication	3	3	6	6	25	25	33	33	44	44
Verbal Limits	6	6	4	4	28	28	31	31	31	31
Student-student Relationships	10	10	9	9	16	16	40	40	25	25
Teacher-parent Relationships	2	2	4	4	14	14	32	32	48	48

TABLE IV
STRATEGIES TO BUILD POSITIVE PARENT-TEACHER RELATIONSHIPS

Strategies	1		2		3		4		5	
	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
Meeting with Parents	3	3	5	5	12	12	34	34	46	46
Contact Parents	2	2	4	4	17	17	35	35	42	42
Compose a Letter	6	6	3	3	15	15	31	31	45	45
Parent-Teacher Conferences	1	1	5	5	21	21	32	32	41	41
Share Good News with Parents	4	4	2	2	16	16	39	39	39	39

When the data in Table III are examined, nearly all the teachers have agreed that the teacher needs to be very careful about his/her verbal limits. When students do not follow rules, procedures and classroom behavioral expectations the teacher needs to describe the appropriate behavior with a neutral body posture and tone of voice, and without using students' names.

Positive relationship is a cornerstone of an effective classroom management. To achieve this, students need to have a feeling of community. Building and fostering positive relationship among students can make a difference in their behaviour and their learning. In this case, teachers can play a significant role to help students to appreciate the strengths and skills that each individual brings to the classroom and respect and appreciate each other, this could include listening to one another and disagreeing in appropriate ways.

The participant teachers of our survey agree that Teacher-Parent relationships are crucial due to the fact that home is called the first school of a child, therefore, the working relationship between teacher and parents can be invaluable to support students' learning, and building good relationships with parents can have a beneficial effect on teacher-child relationships.

One of the key points regarding this is to have strong communication as a fundamental fact to this partnership and to building a sense of community between home and school. In these changing times, teachers should continue to develop and expand their skills in order to maximize effective communication with parents.

Due to the fact that in Iraqi Kurdistan there is no pedagogical universities to graduate professional teachers to teach children at different levels from primary to university, it is noticed that teachers are not sufficiently trained in the skills they need to communicate effectively with parents, and because school communication practices are so fundamental

for involving families in the education process, we suggest that teacher preparation and professional development programs should actively promote the development of communication skills for teachers.

To achieve the above stated aim, we need to break down barriers and foster positive communication between teachers and parents, and engage families to better outcomes for students. Researches show that family engagement promotes student success. Parental engagement with their school community and teachers motivates students to earn higher grades and pass their classes, have better social skills and attend school regularly. When families, teachers and schools find ways to work together, teacher morale rises, student achievement improves, communication increases, and family, school, and community connections can be multiplied.

A degree of trust can be developed when teachers and parents communicate regularly and work collaboratively. Then, if a behavioral concern arises, they are more inclined to respect and support each other.

Because of the above mentioned important role parents may have in the academic and social life of their, we as teachers need to look for ways to involve them in supporting positive classroom behavior.

Read the statements about Teacher-Parent relationships and then put a tick in the box according to the rating scales below:

Strong agree = 5; Agree = 4; Uncertain = 3; Disagree = 2; Strong disagree = 1

Teachers believe that meeting with parents is one of the effective strategies to establish a positive relationship. To have such a relationship means that there would be face-to-face meetings with parents of the students with the purpose of establishing an ongoing conversation, a sense of trust and shared information that will help students considerably.

Another important strategy that participants regard as important is contacting parents. Whenever a problem arises, teachers or administrator of the school has to contact parents so as to find a timely solution. When the parents are contacted they are made aware of and kept abreast of all situations concerning their child. They will be much more supportive for you under these circumstances.

Nearly all the teachers prefer to compose letters to parents in order to provide them with the details of the ongoing feedback about how their children are performing with homework and other important particulars. The content of the letter should include an appreciation for their support and thank them for communicating with you both personally and through the student agenda.

As it is common in Kurdish school, every year at least there would be two Parent-Teacher conferences. Due to this fact all the teachers agree that it is badly important to have such a conference. For tens of years one of the strategies to provide parents with the update on their child's progress was/is parent-teacher conference. Most of the times teachers and administrator of the school tried discuss difficult situations and they took/take this opportunity to get to know the parent and provide information about themselves, their teaching style and positive experiences they had with their child.

Traditionally, teachers shared negative news with the parents of the students but nowadays because of the changes in all the fields of human life and specifically in education teachers need to concentrate on positive behavior of students and surprise them by sharing good news instead of only bad news and this makes parents be more involved. Again all the teachers agree to share not just bad but also good news with parents.

TABLE V
SET UP OF CLASSROOM

Set up of classroom	1		2		3		4		5	
	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
Arranging the Physical Environment of the Classroom	3	3	5	5	12	12	34	34	46	46
Seating Arrangement	2	2	4	4	17	17	35	35	42	42
The Student's Responsibility for Management	6	6	3	3	15	15	31	31	45	45

VIII. CLASSROOM ORGANIZATION

One of the very key parts of how well the students will learn and interact with their classmates and their teacher is the arrangement of the classroom. Classroom setup can dramatically affect students' attitudes toward and habits of learning. Students should be provided an environment that is organized, comfortable and stimulating, in order to learn effectively. Students may easier sense of belonging and ownership when practical physical layouts, supplying diverse materials, are created.

One of the main responsibilities of the teacher in the class is to make sure that his/her classroom is arranged for the students to be productive. Another important responsibility of the teacher in the class is to be sure about the conformity of the students when they enter and the teacher needs to consider whether the classroom is ready for learning. In order to keep the students focus on the lesson and not deter from learning they need to be placed in a well arranged classroom.

The physical surroundings of a class can encourage or inhibit the kind of interaction, and hence learning, which the teacher wants. So as to encourage learning the following three strategies for classroom layout should be considered by the teachers and administrators.

The answer of the participant teachers regarding this issue proves that classroom organization is a key point in order to let teaching and learning take place. The data in Table V shows that the teachers highly prefer Arranging the Physical Environment of the Classroom, Seating Arrangement, and The Student's Responsibility for Management.

Read the statements about classroom organization and then put a tick in the box according to the rating scales below.

Strong agree = 5; Agree = 4; Uncertain = 3; Disagree = 2; Strong disagree = 1

The basic school teachers' response shows that one important way to improve learning and prevent problem behaviours before they occur is the arrangement of the physical environment. The outcome of the researches on the classroom environment has shown that the physical

arrangement can affect the behaviour of both students and teachers, and a well-structured classroom tends to improve student academic and behavioral outcomes. [9]

The spatial structure of the classroom refers to how students are placed, where the teacher and students are in relation to each other, how classroom members move around the room, and the overall sense of atmosphere. According to the outcome of a research which is conducted on the classroom environment suggests that classrooms should be organized to accommodate a variety of activities throughout the day and to meet the teacher's instructional goals [1]

At the same time it is highly recommended that the classroom should be set up to set the stage for the teacher to address the scientific, emotional and social, needs of students. The standards for determining what spatial lay-out is most appropriate to fulfil these functions include: ways to maximize the teacher's ability to see and be seen by all his or her students; facilitate ease of movement throughout the classroom; minimize distractions so that students are best able to actively engage in academics; provide each student and the teacher with his or her own personal space; and ensuring that each student can see presentations and materials posted in the classroom.

One of the key elements which are necessary for children to reenergize themselves and to be able to maintain focus on their school work is physical activity throughout the school day because physically children can be positively affected by involving them in movement activities. These activities can be initiated by teachers throughout the day and especially during classroom transitions. Cognitively children can be reinforced by using songs and rhymes lessons that improve their listening and memory skills. These activities can be in the form of role plays, seat-changes, games and dance which they may actively contribute to their developing basic timing, coordination and concentration. Educators have noted fewer behavior problems when children are provided with many opportunities to move.

The traditional arrangement for classrooms typically consists of about five or six straight lines, each containing five to seven chairs equidistant from each other. Historically, it is witnessed, the straight-row arrangement evolved to make the best use of the only adequate lighting then available-natural light from side windows and another factor of this kind of seating arrangement was the height of the students. Due to the technological development in lighting, natural light is not the only source of lightening in the class and in spite of developments in this field of technology this traditional arrangement persists, in fact dominates. A survey of classrooms which is recently conducted on a university campus found over 90 percent of the classrooms to have this arrangement.

As it is mentioned above, the traditional straight row arrangement is common in most educational settings, particularly in primary upper elementary through high school and in college settings. The cause of this dominance is difficult to find but tradition is the explanation offered most frequently. As a result of discussions with some teachers who employ the strait-row arrangement yielded other reactions as

well. Many teachers commented that they simply had never thought about it. Some other teachers said that the school janitor would become angry if the seats were rearranged. Others reported trying different arrangements but they have been rebuked by colleagues or superiors for having or leaving a "messy room". Some teachers simply showed that they liked their room in this traditional way without any explanation for why they had that preference.

TABLE VI
 STUDENT'S RESPONSIBILITY FOR DISCIPLINE

Student's Responsibility For Discipline	1		2		3		4		5	
	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
Responsibility For Academic Work	3	3	5	5	12	12	34	34	46	46
Student's Responsibility Regarding Attendance And Tardiness	2	2	4	4	17	17	35	35	42	42

More than half a century ago John Dewey attacked this arrangement because it prevents experimentation in the classroom. Many writers in education have agreed almost unanimously. Whenever seating arrangement is discussed in a teaching method course, the traditional arrangement is virtually always attacked as less desirable than other alternatives. [2]

The response of the teachers indicates that instruction is much easier when teacher knows what students expect from him. To do so, each member of a class must cooperate and assume certain responsibilities. Student's responsibility lies at the very core of classroom management. When a student feels like an important member of the classroom, the students will not only be more excited to be at school but be more willing to contribute in the classroom as well. Students must have a sense of purpose and feel as though they are needed in the classroom.

As students have the right to a free public education, they are also responsible for complying with the rules and regulations of the school district, the instructions of all school district personnel, and for accepting the authority of the faculty and school district officials on school property. Failure to meet these responsibilities will be cause for disciplinary action.

The student is responsible for his/her own success in the learning process. One of the key points in education is to actively involve student in the learning process and should behave appropriately for a learning environment. When the teacher sets appropriate rules for classroom behavior and enforces them, and she/he comes to class each day to teach, then student has responsibilities. When the student accepts her/his responsibilities, the leader of the class who is the teacher can give more classroom time to instruction. Students' responsibilities for their own behavior are many. These responsibilities can be in the form of self-discipline, self-regulation, self-management, self-control, social skills and more. The common theme running through all of these discussions is that students should be given the message that

they are responsible for their own behavior, and that they should be provided with guidelines and training to realize that control.

Read the statements about Student's Responsibility for Discipline and then put a tick in the box according to the rating scales below.

Strong agree = 5; Agree = 4; Uncertain = 3; Disagree = 2; Strong disagree = 1

Nearly all the teachers believe that the students should feel responsibility for his/her Academic Work. The student is responsible for completing class assignments including quizzes and tests on time and according to the instructions given by the teachers. A student who has been excused from school has the right and responsibility to make up the work missed during any excused absence. Students are responsible for bringing to class all materials required for daily classroom use like book, paper, pen, pencil, calculator, etc., and taking proper care of his/her book and returning it at the end of the course.

The student is responsible for remaining quiet and on task during class time so as not to disrupt the learning of other students.

The student is responsible to display a serious intention to learn. The student should feel responsibility for communicating any concerns to teacher and participating in all class discussions and question-and-answer sessions.

As it is shown in Table VI, teachers badly prefer Student's Responsibility Regarding Attendance and Tardiness. The student is responsible for attending class at the beginning of the school day. Students arriving late are to report to the proper school authorities, as designated by their local school rules.

If absence from school is necessary because of illness or other legitimate reasons, students are responsible for bringing a written excuse signed by a parent or guardian upon return to school. Absence or tardiness of students because of religious holidays and observances shall be recorded as excused absences or tardiness at the written request of the parent.

In order to excuse students before the end of the day, they should bring a written request signed by a parent or guardian to the school office, preferably upon arrival at school.

Sufficient time is allowed between classes for students to arrive at the next class on time. If a student is detained after class by a teacher, a pass should be obtained from that teacher so that tardiness will be excused in the next class.

During a class hour, students shall not leave a classroom without a pass from the teacher. Under no conditions shall a student leave school during the day without permission of the school administration.

A student leaving the building without proper authorization may be subject to disciplinary action.

The student is responsible to maintain an acceptable level of personal hygiene, and comply with all stated university rules and regulations.

IX. CONCLUSION

The art of classroom management has been argued for many decades. In order to have successful classroom management teachers should guide force in the classroom and students also should take responsibilities in this area. However, useful strategies are available for teachers who want to help students make a significant contribution to the classroom management effort.

As students gradually learn to play an authentic part in their own learning, they should develop a commitment to both their individual success and that of the larger classroom community. Citizenship education thus occurs when a teacher works with students as partners in developing a positive learning community (in contrast to imposing a system to control them). The result can be a win-win situation: the teacher gradually lets go of some care-taking responsibilities and spends more energy on teaching, and students are empowered by new responsibilities and freedoms. Students can do more than just talk about democracy—they can make informed and responsible decisions that translate into learning democracy.

Any good teacher should be able to play various roles in the classroom, but without doubt the most important one is the art of classroom management. The main reason behind this is the fact that effective teaching and learning cannot take place in a poorly managed classroom. Both teachers and students suffer badly when students are disorderly and disrespectful, and no apparent rules and chaos becomes the norm. In these situations, teachers work hard to teach but students most likely learn much less than they should. In contrast, teaching and learning can flourish when well managed classrooms is provided. But a well-managed classroom takes a good deal of effort to create—and the person who is most responsible for creating it is the teacher.

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